

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Title: SOP for PALscript Editor to modify methods created using TriPlus RSH Sampling

Workflow Editor

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Version: version 1

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Summary

PALscript Editor allows more feature control and changing of settings for optimising methods developed for the TriPlus RSH autosampler. In this procedure, an example of method editing for optimising automation of derivatisation based on 'SOP for on-line sequential 2 step derivatization method creation using TriPlus RSH Sampling Workflow Editor' is shown.

Software

- PALscript Editor version 3.1 beta
- TriPlus RSH Sampling Workflow Editor (SWE) from ThermoFisher version 1.4.0.4

Procedure:

1. The method created in SWE need to be saved as Script XML (*.xml format)
2. Open PALscript Editor
3. SW need to be connected to the instrument to edit the method according modules and tools installed on the autosampler:
 - a. Select PAL3>connect

- b. In the pop-up window select the endpoint address of Autosampler and choose a role: example GC3 need to be different to the role selected in other SWs (e.g. for SWE role selected GC1)

- c. List of modules can be visualised if not go to views and tick PAL Modules

4. Import the .xml method: Script>Import

5. The method imported is the automation of derivatisation needs removing of extra opening closing doors of cooler drawer that is not possible to edit in SWE this version:
 - a. Initially, the cooler drawer door is set to be closed after each individual step added in SWE
 - b. Some steps of closing drawer are slow the workflow and are unnecessary
 - c. locate all unnecessary steps (when opening the door to pipette reagent keep it open when rinsing syringe with reagent and for second reagent pipetting and dispensing to the sample's vial)
 - d. In the activity "leaveObject" change the False default value of leaving door open to true:
`LeaveObject(leaveDrawerOpen=true)`
6. Once finished with all the modifications, export the modified method
 - a. Select Script>export

```

PALScript Editor Beta - internal use only
File Edit Script Execution PAL3 Settings View ?
Validate F6
Export
Import
PMC_Script
867
868
869
870
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873
874
875
876
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878
879
880
volume_31,
penetrationDepth = injectorPen
injectorPenetrationSpeed = injectorPen
injectionFlowRate = injectionFlowRate_
preInjectionDwellTime = preInjectionDw
postInjectionDwellTime = postInjection
injectionSignalMode = injectionSignalM

SetStatus( key = "Message", "Clean Syringe - post

Clean_Syringe(
washSource = washSource_32,
washIndex = washIndex_32,
washCycles = washCycles_32,

```

- b. A pop up window ask to first save the method on disk select ok and save the method as PALscript File (*.PALscript)

- c. A pop up window is opened containing a list of method's parameters to set, also description of the edited method can be added

- d. Parameters already defined are ticked as read only for the ones that need to be changed when uploaded in the sequence need to be tick off (e.g. here positions of MSTFA and MeOX reagents to be defined later as multiple reagents aliquots are placed on the cooler drawer)

